

MERSEA IP

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the European Area - Integrated Project

Delivery 9.1.1

Nesting code for NEMO

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The logo for Ifremer, featuring a stylized fish and the word "Ifremer" in black on a yellow background.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Ultimately, the Mersea project has to demonstrate the European capacity to connect different regional components into a single operational one. In this perspective, the current NEMO/EOMF system needs a set of improvements but also additional physical implementations to be used, in particular, as a shelf seas model.

Among all of the deliverables listed in the sub-task 9.1, we will only deal in this report with the treatment of open-boundaries conditions. Concerning pre-processing tools, a set of interpolations routines to create boundary/initial data is described in the first part, while the second part is devoted to the implementation of a new nesting scheme in OPA: the “Flow relaxation Scheme” (Davies-1976, Engedahl-1995). An original characteristic of this development is that it deals with unstructured open boundaries. It is thus possible with this methodology to force the OPA model either with complex or straight open-boundaries. This requirement was principally needed for the MRCS model, part of the MERSEA system (Its open boundaries partially follow isobaths contours as seen on Figure 1).

Figure 1: MRCS (Medium-Resolution Continental Shelf) model domain run at the UK MET Office. Straight red lines delimit the global domain, while green lines define the position of unstructured open boundaries (courtesy of A. Sellar).

2. INTERPOLATION TOOLS

This section describes interpolation programs (written in Fortran 90) to create initial and boundary data for a regional configuration from outputs from a larger scale model. All of these routines read and produce files in NetCdf format with conventions described in the sub-section 2.1. For flexibility, interpolation procedures have been separated in 2d (horizontal) and 1d (vertical) interpolation. Therefore, their combination allows the transformation of fields from/to any kind of vertical coordinate system. Moreover, in the following, we do not make any assumptions concerning the horizontal discretisation of variables.

2.1. Input files conventions

2.1.1. Grid variables

The different programs presented below need a source and a destination NetCdf grid file. These contain all the necessary information to perform 1d and 2d interpolations on a spherical domain. Each file must contain the grid variables and dimensions as listed in table 1. Longitude and latitude are two-dimensional arrays given in degrees. In the case of vertical interpolation one has to provide a depth array given in meters. It could either be 1 dimensional (z-coordinate model case) or 3 dimensional (sigma coordinate/isopycnal/hybrid vertical coordinate model case). Mask array equals 0 over land and 1 elsewhere. Grid_cos and grid_sin are respectively the cosine and sine of the angle between the local grid face and the North direction¹. Note that they are necessary only for vector's rotation if the destination's grid horizontal framework differs from the source's grid one. An example of "Ncdump" output of a grid file is given on Figure 2.

Dimensions	Variables	
	<i>Input/Output grid variables</i>	<i>Input data variables</i>
X	Longitude (x, y)	Var (x, y)
	Latitude (x, y)	or
Y	Depth(z) or Depth(x, y, z)	Var (x, y, t)
Z	Mask (x, y, z)	or
T	grid_cos (x, y)*	Var (x, y, z)
	grid_sin (x, y)*	or
		Var (x, y, z, t)

Table 1: Dimensions and variables name conventions for input/output grid or data NetCdf files. *grid_cos and grid_sin variables are optional (only in the case of vector rotation).

¹ For example, in the case of a regular C-grid, at U velocity points, grid_cos and grid_sin would respectively be 0 and 1 everywhere.

```

netcdf PSY2V1R1_GAS_GRIDT {
dimensions:
    y = 176 ;
    x = 179 ;
    z = 43 ;
variables:
    float depth(z) ;
        depth:long_name = "depth" ;
        depth:standard_name = "depth" ;
        depth:units = "Meters" ;
        depth:positive = "down" ;
        depth:unit_long = "m" ;
        depth:axis = "Z" ;
        depth:valid_min = 3.13f ;
        depth:valid_max = 5650.943f ;
    float latitude(y, x) ;
        latitude:long_name = "latitude" ;
        latitude:standard_name = "latitude" ;
        latitude:units = "degrees_north" ;
        latitude:unit_long = "Degrees North" ;
        latitude:axis = "Y" ;
        latitude:valid_min = 39.39587f ;
        latitude:valid_max = 52.95009f ;
    float longitude(y, x) ;
        longitude:long_name = "longitude" ;
        longitude:standard_name = "longitude" ;
        longitude:units = "degrees_east" ;
        longitude:unit_long = "Degrees East" ;
        longitude:axis = "X" ;
        longitude:valid_min = -13.71795f ;
        longitude:valid_max = 5.618435f ;
    int mask(z, y, x) ;
        mask:units = "unitless" ;
        mask:_Fillvalue = 9999 ;
        mask:missing_value = 9999 ;
        mask:valid_min = 0 ;
        mask:valid_max = 1 ;

    // global attributes:
        :title = "PSY2 zoom at Tracer points" ;
        :history = "2004/12/16 11:55:43 MERCATOR Netcdf creation" ;
        :source = "MERCATOR PSY2V1" ;
        :institution = "GIP MERCATOR OCEAN" ;
        :references = "http://www.mercator.com.fr" ;
        :conventions = "CF-1.0" ;
        :domain_name = "ATL" ;
        :forecast_type = "hindcast" ;
        :bulletin_type = "offline" ;
        :longitude_min = -13.71795f ;
        :longitude_max = 5.618435f ;
        :latitude_min = 39.39587f ;
        :latitude_max = 52.95009f ;
}
    
```

Figure 2: Example of a "Ncdump" output of a grid file from a z-coordinate model.

2.1.2. Data variables

Variable to be processed in NetCdf input files must belong to one of the different kinds listed in Table 1. Apart from the 3 geographical dimensions, an input variable can have an additional dimension t (generally time). Note that It is assumed that horizontal fields (Var (x,

y), $\text{Var}(x, y, t)$) correspond to surface values². An example of Ncdump output of such a file is given on Figure 3.

```
netcdf PSY2V1R1_ESEOAT_GRIDT_ANA_20030210 {
dimensions:
    x = 311 ;
    y = 116 ;
    z = 43 ;
    t = UNLIMITED ; // (1 currently)
variables:
    float longitude(y, x) ;
        longitude:long_name = "longitude" ;
        longitude:standard_name = "longitude" ;
        longitude:units = "degrees_east" ;
        longitude:unit_long = "Degrees East" ;
        longitude:axis = "X" ;
        longitude:valid_min = -85.97446f ;
        longitude:valid_max = -24.09345f ;
    float latitude(y, x) ;
        latitude:long_name = "latitude" ;
        latitude:standard_name = "latitude" ;
        latitude:units = "degrees_north" ;
        latitude:unit_long = "Degrees North" ;
        latitude:axis = "Y" ;
        latitude:valid_min = 62.24984f ;
        latitude:valid_max = 72.56667f ;
    float depth(z) ;
        depth:long_name = "depth" ;
        depth:standard_name = "depth" ;
        depth:units = "Meters" ;
        depth:positive = "down" ;
        depth:unit_long = "m" ;
        depth:axis = "Z" ;
        depth:valid_min = 3.13f ;
        depth:valid_max = 5650.943f ;
    float time(t) ;
        time:long_name = "time" ;
        time:standard_name = "time" ;
        time:units = "days since 1950-01-01 00:00:00" ;
        time:unit_long = "days since 1950-01-01 00:00:00" ;
        time:time_origin = "1950-01-01 00:00:00" ;
        time:step = 1.f ;
        time:axis = "T" ;
    float temperature(t, z, y, x) ;
        temperature:long_name = "temperature" ;
        temperature:standard_name = "sea_water_potential_temperature" ;
        temperature:units = "Degrees Celcius" ;
        temperature:unit_long = "degC" ;
        temperature:_Fillvalue = 1.e+35f ;
        temperature:missing_value = 1.e+35f ;
        temperature:valid_min = -3.104976f ;
        temperature:valid_max = 7.209938f ;

// global attributes:
    :title = "PSY2 zoom at Tracer points" ;
    :history = "2005/04/ 1 16:29:48 MERCATOR Netcdf creation" ;
    :source = "MERCATOR PSY2V1" ;
    :institution = "GIP MERCATOR OCEAN" ;
    :references = "http://www.mercator.com.fr" ;
    :conventions = "CF-1.0" ;
    :domain_name = "ATL" ;
    :forecast_type = "hindcast" ;
```

Figure 3: Example of input Netcdf file containing variables to interpolate.

² As a matter of fact, their missing values are given by the first depth layer of the mask(x, y, z) array.

2.2. Horizontal interpolation/extrapolation

The core of the two-dimensional interpolation procedure is a slightly modified version of the SCRIP³ package. Modifications of the original code essentially consist in changing the input/output grids/masks conventions to accept standard NetCdf output files from OPA (Table 1) and adding horizontal extrapolation. Since grid point search can be relatively long, 2d interpolations are performed in the two steps described below: first compute weights once for all, then remap.

2.2.1. Interpolation weights

The modified scrip program computes interpolation weights to horizontally remap fields from one grid to another. Edit the namelist *scrip3d.in* (see example on Figure 4) to provide the source grid file name (**grid1_file**), the destination's grid name (**grid2_file**) and the name of the NetCdf remapping weights file (**interp_file**). The **map_method** corresponds to the name of the interpolation procedure: **distwgt** for remapping with the four nearest points weighted by their distance to the destination's grid point, **bilinear** for bilinear remapping and **bicubic** for bicubic interpolation. Extrapolation to the four nearest unmasked points at each depth level weighted by their distance is performed if the logical variable **extrap** is true. In this case, if the variable **use_dst_mask** is true, the destination's grid mask is used to restrict the number of extrapolated points. Otherwise, every masked points are extrapolated as long as the distance to the closest unmasked point is less than the **dist_extrap_max** parameter (50 km by default). Finally, **restrict_type** is the restriction search method: choosing **latitude** restricts the search by dividing the source grid into **num_srch_bins** latitude bins while **latlon** divides the source grid in **num_srch_bins** in both directions.

```

&scrip3d_inputs
  grid1_file = '../DATA/PSY2_GAS_GRIDT.NC'
  grid2_file = '../DATA/MARS_GAS_GRIDT.NC'
  interp_file = '../DATA/rmp_PSY2GAS_to_MARSGAS_bicub_T2T.NC'
  map_name = 'PSY2 GAS T grid to MARS GAS T grid'
  use_dst_mask = .false.
  extrap = .true.
  map_method = 'bicubic'
  restrict_type = 'latitude'
  num_srch_bins = 90
/
    
```

Figure 4: Example of namelist for the interpolation weight computation.

2.2.2. 2d remapping

2.2.2.1. Scalar variables

Once the interpolation weights have been computed, use the remap program to transform any variable from the source grid on the destination's one. The output file is given at the horizontal locations of the destination grid, but at the constant z-levels of the input grid. An example of its syntax is given on Figure 5. The user should specify names of the input (**in.nc**) and output (**out.nc**) files, the output grid file (**outgrid.nc**) and the name of the weight file (**wgt.nc**). Other inputs in brackets are optional. If grid arrays are not included in the input file, the name of an input grid file (**ingrid.nc**) must be specified.

³ SCRIP: A Spherical Coordinate Remapping and Interpolation Package by Philip Jones. See <http://climate.lanl.gov/Software/SCRIP/> for detailed informations.

By default, all the variables depending on dimension x and y (see Table 1) are interpolated unless the name of the variable (**variable**) is given. Specify option **-E** to extrapolate, **-U** to apply destination's grid mask, **-A** to append any existing output file and **-M** to write a mask array in the output file.

```

remap usage : remap -i in.nc -og outgrid.nc -w wgt.nc -o out.nc [-ig
ingrid.nc] [-v variable] [-E] [-U] [-M] [-A]

-E          : Extrapolates
-U          : Use destination grid mask
-M          : Write output mask
-A          : Append existing file if any
variable    : Variable to process
in.nc       : Input netcdf file
ingrid.nc   : Input grid netcdf file
outgrid.nc  : Output grid netcdf file
wgt.nc      : Weights netcdf file
out.nc      : Output netcdf file
    
```

Figure 5: Syntax for scalar remapping program.

2.2.2.2. Vector variables

If each source and destination grid faces have the same orientation, the remap program can be used also for vector variables. In the other case, a rotation must be performed by using the remap_vec program. Its syntax is given on Figure 6 is similar to the scalar remapping program except that all inputs are needed for each vector component. Using cosine and sine variables in the input and output grid files, it remaps, separately, each vector component in the Cartesian coordinate system.

```

remap_vec usage : remap_vec -iu in1.nc -iv in2.nc -og outgrid.nc -wu wgt1.nc
-wv wgt2.nc -viu variable1 -viv variable2          -vo variableout -o out.nc
[-igu ingrid1.nc] [-igv ingrid2.nc] [-E] [-U] [-M] [-A]

-E          : Extrapolates
-U          : Use destination grid mask
-M          : Write output mask
-A          : Append existing file if any
in1.nc      : Input netcdf file for 1st vector component
in2.nc      : Input netcdf file for 2nd vector component
variable1   : Variable to process in file in1.nc
variable2   : Variable to process in file in2.nc
ingrid1.nc  : Input grid netcdf file for 1st vector component
ingrid2.nc  : Input grid netcdf file for 2nd vector component
outgrid.nc  : Output grid netcdf file
wgt1.nc     : Weights file for 1st component on dest grid
wgt2.nc     : Weights file for 2nd component on dest grid
out.nc      : Output netcdf file
variableout : Output variable name in out.nc file
    
```

Figure 6: Syntax for vector remapping program.

2.3. Vertical interpolation

Use the interp1d program (its syntax is shown on Figure 7) to remap a variable in the vertical. The routine needs depths arrays that can be either 1d or 3d (see Table 1). Three interpolation methods are available: linear, cubic, and spline. Extrapolation to the nearest unmasked point on the vertical is performed if option **-E**. **-U** options applies the destination grid mask. If the latter option is not defined, note that extrapolation would be performed everywhere on the vertical, as it is done for the horizontal remapping program.

```
interpld usage : interpld -i in.nc -og outgrid.nc -o out.nc
-m method [-ig ingrid.nc] [-v variable] [-E] [-U] [-M] [-A]

-E      : Extrapolates
-U      : Use destination grid mask
-M      : Write output mask
-A      : Append existing file if any
method  : linear/cubic/spline
variable : Variable to process
in.nc   : Input netcdf file
ingrid.nc : Input grid netcdf file
outgrid.nc : Output grid netcdf file
out.nc  : Output netcdf file
```

Figure 7: Syntax for the vertical interpolation program.

3. UNSTRUCTURED OPEN BOUNDARIES FOR NEMO

3.1. The Flow Relaxation Scheme

The Flow Relaxation Scheme (hereafter FRS), designed by Davies (1976), is a simple way to relax the solution of a limited area model in the vicinity of its open boundaries to the solution of a large-scale model (or to climatological data). If d is the discrete distance from the open boundary and N the width of the FRS zone, it can be written for any prognostic variable Φ as the following combination:

$$\Phi(d) = \alpha(d)\Phi_e(d) + (1 - \alpha(d))\Phi_c(d) \quad d = 1, N \quad (1)$$

where Φ_e is the external solution and Φ_c the effective model solution. The relaxation parameter $\alpha(d)$ varies between 0 (at the inner ends of the FRS zone) to 1 at the open boundary limit where the model solution is completely prescribed ($\Phi = \Phi_e$). Note that it can be easily shown that using this scheme is completely equivalent to an additional relaxation term in each prognostic equations of the form:

$$-\frac{1}{\tau}(\Phi - \Phi_e) \quad (2)$$

The relaxation time scale τ depends on the model time step Δt and the weight function:

$$\tau = \Delta t \frac{1 - \alpha}{\alpha} \quad (3)$$

In the implementation described below, following Palma and Matano (2000), we will use for α an expression of the form (see Figure 8):

$$\alpha(d) = 1 - \tanh\left(\frac{1}{2}(d-1)\right) \quad d = 1, N \quad (4)$$

Figure 8: Weight function α for the Flow Relaxation Scheme.

3.2. Numerical implementation

3.2.1. Algorithmic structure

For simplicity, the way the FRS has been implemented in NEMO is very similar to what has been done for the existing Open Boundary Conditions (OBC) scheme for straight boundaries. As a matter of fact, most of the new routines (with prefix **bdy**) have their counterparts for the OBC scheme (with prefix **obc**).

The FRS has been implemented for the free surface version only. As for the OBC scheme in this case, we have supposed a zero gradient condition normal to the open boundary interface for the sea surface height (SSH). Thus, equation (1) needs to be applied only for temperature (T), salinity (S), and each velocity component (U, V).

Figure 9: OPA call tree with new routines for the FRS in grey.

The call tree on Figure 9 shows the main routines called when the cpp key **key_bdy** is defined. The initialisation of the unstructured open boundaries is done in the routine **bdy_init** where several arrays necessary for the definition of the unstructured boundaries are read (see section 3.2.2.1). Then, at each time step, the **bdy_dta** routine reads and temporally interpolates boundary data. The update of dynamics and tracers is done respectively in the **bdy_dyn** routine (called in **dyn_spg_fsc**) and the **bdy_tra** routine (called

in *tra_nxt*) where next step variables (after fields) are replaced by using the combination (1). Concerning existing routines, *sol_mat* has been modified to account for the SSH gradient condition and the velocity horizontal divergence has also been set to zero on open boundaries in *div_cur*. Since the specification of the velocities does not ensure the global volume conservation, an additional routine, *bdy_vol*, corrects the net transport through open boundaries in order to do so. This procedure is finally similar to what was originally proposed by Marchesiello et al. (2001) and largely inspired from the existing *obc_vol* routine (see technical report from Talandier and Tréguier-2002).

3.2.2. Boundary data/initialization files

Three files corresponding respectively to variables at T, U and V points are necessary to use the FRS. Each of them contains arrays for the definition of unstructured open boundaries and the data itself. These are read with existing IOIPSL routines and with a new module (*iobdy*). Ncdump outputs examples are given on Figure 11, Figure 12 and Figure 13.

3.2.2.1. Initialisation arrays

- *bdy_msk* is a 2-dimensionnal mask defining the computational zone in the global rectangular domain⁴. It is 1 inside the open boundaries and 0 elsewhere. It is used to update masks in the code and to compute normal directions to the open boundary (for volume conservation). Only the mask at T-points is read.
- *nbidta*, *nbdta* arrays contain respectively i and j horizontal indices of points to relax relative to the global domain⁴. One has to respect the same conventions used for straight open boundaries: The open boundary itself is defined at dynamical points. Prescribed tracers points must be located outside this domain (Figure 10).
- *nbrdta* is the “discrete distance” to the open boundary used to compute the weight function (equation 4). *nbrdta*=1 for the specified points. In the following, it has been computed recursively by considering that whenever a point has a neighbour with *nbrdta*=d, its distance to the boundary is d+1. The maximum distance should be given in each file by the global attribute *rimwidth*.

Figure 10: Example of unstructured open boundary and prescribed points (*nbrdta*=1).

⁴ We mean by “global domain” the bathymetry/data domain in the code of size *jpjtda* x *jpjtda*.

3.2.2.2. *Data arrays*

Vertical profiles of temperature, salinity and velocity components must be given at ***nbidta***, ***nbdta*** indices as shown on Figure 11 to Figure 13. Note that there is a dummy dimension ***yb*** to use IOIPSL reading routines. If boundary data is not applied in a cyclic way (see namelist options in subsection 3.2.3.2), time information is read in the ***time_counter*** variable (it must be identical in each file). The time origin and the calendar type are read from the ***time_counter*** attributes and are used to convert the time array for temporal linear interpolation to the model time step.

Other arrays (***nav_lon***, ***nav_lat*** and ***depth***) are not used in the code but could be useful for an eventual visualisation.

```

netcdf bdydata_grid_T {
dimensions:
    x = 202 ;
    y = 104 ;
    xb = 2058 ;
    yb = 1 ;
    depth = 40 ;
    time_counter = UNLIMITED ; // (61 currently)
variables:
    float nav_lon(y, x) ;
        nav_lon:units = "degrees_east" ;
        nav_lon:valid_min = 0.f ;
        nav_lon:valid_max = 1005.f ;
        nav_lon:long_name = "Longitude" ;
    float nav_lat(y, x) ;
        nav_lat:units = "degrees_north" ;
        nav_lat:valid_min = 0.f ;
        nav_lat:valid_max = 515.f ;
        nav_lat:long_name = "Latitude" ;
    float time_counter(time_counter) ;
        time_counter:units = "seconds since 1992-01-01 00:00:00" ;
        time_counter:calendar = "noleap" ;
        time_counter:title = "Time" ;
        time_counter:long_name = "Time axis" ;
        time_counter:time_counter_origin = "1992-Jan-01 00:00:00" ;
    float depth(depth) ;
        depth:units = "model_levels" ;
        depth:valid_min = 59.9493f ;
        depth:valid_max = 4042.771f ;
        depth:long_name = "Model levels" ;
    float bdy_msk(y, x) ;
        bdy_msk:units = "unitless" ;
        bdy_msk:missing_value = 1.e+20f ;
        bdy_msk:long_name = "Unstructured boundary mask" ;
    int nbidta(yb, xb) ;
        nbidta:units = "unitless" ;
        nbidta:valid_min = 2 ;
        nbidta:valid_max = 200 ;
        nbidta:long_name = "Bdy i indices" ;
    int nbjdta(yb, xb) ;
        nbjdta:units = "unitless" ;
        nbjdta:valid_min = 3 ;
        nbjdta:valid_max = 102 ;
        nbjdta:long_name = "Bdy j indices" ;
    int nbrdta(yb, xb) ;
        nbrdta:units = "unitless" ;
        nbrdta:valid_min = 1 ;
        nbrdta:valid_max = 10 ;
        nbrdta:long_name = "Bdy discrete distance" ;
    float votemper(time_counter, depth, yb, xb) ;
        votemper:units = "C" ;
        votemper:missing_value = 0.f ;
        votemper:valid_min = 10.f ;
        votemper:valid_max = 10.f ;
        votemper:long_name = "Temperature" ;
        votemper:short_name = "votemper" ;
    float vosaline(time_counter, depth, yb, xb) ;
        vosaline:units = "PSU" ;
        vosaline:missing_value = 0.f ;
        vosaline:valid_min = 35.5f ;
        vosaline:valid_max = 35.5f ;
        vosaline:long_name = "Salinity" ;
        vosaline:short_name = "vosaline" ;

    // global attributes:
        :title = "Unstructured boundaries data file at T-points" ;
        :history = "01-Mar-2005 11:31:44" ;
        :institution = "GIP MERCATOR OCEAN" ;
        :references = "http://www.mercator-ocean.fr" ;
        :rinwidth = 10 ;
}
    
```

Figure 11: Ncdump output example of boundary data file at T-points.

```

netcdf bdydata_grid_U {
dimensions:
    x = 202 ;
    y = 104 ;
    xb = 2058 ;
    yb = 1 ;
    depth = 40 ;
    time_counter = UNLIMITED ; // (61 currently)
variables:
    float nav_lon(y, x) ;
        nav_lon:units = "degrees_east" ;
        nav_lon:valid_min = 2.5f ;
        nav_lon:valid_max = 1007.5f ;
        nav_lon:long_name = "Longitude" ;
    float nav_lat(y, x) ;
        nav_lat:units = "degrees_north" ;
        nav_lat:valid_min = 0.f ;
        nav_lat:valid_max = 515.f ;
        nav_lat:long_name = "Latitude" ;
    float depth(depth) ;
        depth:units = "model_levels" ;
        depth:valid_min = 59.9493f ;
        depth:valid_max = 4042.771f ;
        depth:long_name = "Model levels" ;
    float time_counter(time_counter) ;
        time_counter:units = "seconds since 1992-01-01 00:00:00" ;
        time_counter:calendar = "noleap" ;
        time_counter:title = "Time" ;
        time_counter:long_name = "Time axis" ;
        time_counter:time_counter_origin = "1992-Jan-01 00:00:00" ;
    float bdy_msk(y, x) ;
        bdy_msk:units = "unitless" ;
        bdy_msk:missing_value = 1.e+20f ;
        bdy_msk:long_name = "Unstructured boundary mask" ;
    int nbidta(yb, xb) ;
        nbidta:units = "unitless" ;
        nbidta:valid_min = 2 ;
        nbidta:valid_max = 199 ;
        nbidta:long_name = "Bdy i indices" ;
    int nbjdta(yb, xb) ;
        nbjdta:units = "unitless" ;
        nbjdta:valid_min = 3 ;
        nbjdta:valid_max = 102 ;
        nbjdta:long_name = "Bdy j indices" ;
    int nbrdta(yb, xb) ;
        nbrdta:units = "unitless" ;
        nbrdta:valid_min = 1 ;
        nbrdta:valid_max = 10 ;
        nbrdta:long_name = "Bdy discrete distance" ;
    float vozocrtx(time_counter, depth, yb, xb) ;
        vozocrtx:units = "m/s" ;
        vozocrtx:missing_value = 0.f ;
        vozocrtx:valid_min = 0.1096174f ;
        vozocrtx:valid_max = 0.415823f ;
        vozocrtx:long_name = "Zonal Current" ;
        vozocrtx:short_name = "vozocrtx" ;

    // global attributes:
        :title = "Unstructured boundaries data file at U-points" ;
        :history = "01-Mar-2005 11:31:57" ;
        :institution = "GIP MERCATOR OCEAN" ;
        :references = "http://www.mercator-ocean.fr" ;
        :rimwidth = 10 ;
}
    
```

Figure 12: Ncdump output example of boundary data file at U-points.

```

netcdf bdydata_grid_V {
dimensions:
    x = 202 ;
    y = 104 ;
    xb = 2037 ;
    yb = 1 ;
    depth = 40 ;
    time_counter = UNLIMITED ; // (61 currently)
variables:
    float nav_lon(y, x) ;
        nav_lon:units = "degrees_east" ;
        nav_lon:valid_min = 0.f ;
        nav_lon:valid_max = 1005.f ;
        nav_lon:long_name = "Longitude" ;
    float nav_lat(y, x) ;
        nav_lat:units = "degrees_north" ;
        nav_lat:valid_min = 2.5f ;
        nav_lat:valid_max = 517.5f ;
        nav_lat:long_name = "Latitude" ;
    float depth(depth) ;
        depth:units = "model_levels" ;
        depth:valid_min = 59.9493f ;
        depth:valid_max = 4042.771f ;
        depth:long_name = "Model levels" ;
    float time_counter(time_counter) ;
        time_counter:units = "seconds since 1992-01-01 00:00:00" ;
        time_counter:calendar = "noleap" ;
        time_counter:title = "Time" ;
        time_counter:long_name = "Time axis" ;
        time_counter:time_counter_origin = "1992-Jan-01 00:00:00" ;
    float bdy_msk(y, x) ;
        bdy_msk:units = "unitless" ;
        bdy_msk:missing_value = 1.e+20f ;
        bdy_msk:long_name = "Unstructured boundary mask" ;
    int nbidta(yb, xb) ;
        nbidta:units = "unitless" ;
        nbidta:valid_min = 2 ;
        nbidta:valid_max = 199 ;
        nbidta:long_name = "Bdy i indices" ;
    int nbjdtta(yb, xb) ;
        nbjdtta:units = "unitless" ;
        nbjdtta:valid_min = 3 ;
        nbjdtta:valid_max = 101 ;
        nbjdtta:long_name = "Bdy j indices" ;
    int nbrdta(yb, xb) ;
        nbrdta:units = "unitless" ;
        nbrdta:valid_min = 1 ;
        nbrdta:valid_max = 10 ;
        nbrdta:long_name = "Bdy discrete distance" ;
    float vomecrty(time_counter, depth, yb, xb) ;
        vomecrty:units = "m/s" ;
        vomecrty:missing_value = 0.f ;
        vomecrty:valid_min = -0.1307546f ;
        vomecrty:valid_max = 0.1584143f ;
        vomecrty:long_name = "Meridional Current" ;
        vomecrty:short_name = "vomecrty" ;

    // global attributes:
        :title = "Unstructured boundaries data file at V-points" ;
        :history = "01-Mar-2005 11:32:00" ;
        :institution = "GIP MERCATOR OCEAN" ;
        :references = "http://www.mercator-ocean.fr" ;
        :rinwidth = 10 ;
}
    
```

Figure 13: Ncdump output example of boundary data file at V-points.

3.2.3. User-defined parameters

3.2.3.1. Maximum dimensions

Since no dynamic allocation is allowed in the code, the user has to provide the following maximum dimensions in the *bdy_par* module (see Figure 14):

- The maximum length of the boundary data in file (*jpbdta*)
- The maximum length of boundary data on a processor (*jpbdim*)
- The maximum number of time dumps in boundary data files (*jpbttime*)

```

MODULE bdy_par
  !!=====
  !!          *** MODULE bdy_par ***
  !! Unstructured Open Boundary Cond. :  define related parameters
  !!=====
  #if defined key_bdy
  !!-----
  !!  'key_bdy' :                               Unstructured Open Boundary Condition
  !!-----
  !! history :
  !!  9.0  01/05  (J. Chanut, A. Sellar) Original code
  !!-----
  !! * Modules used
  USE par_oce          ! ocean parameters

  IMPLICIT NONE
  PUBLIC

  LOGICAL, PUBLIC, PARAMETER ::  lk_bdy = .TRUE.  !: Unstructured Ocean
                                              !Boundary Condition flag

  !!-----
  !! Unstructured open boundary parameters
  !!-----

  INTEGER, PARAMETER ::  &
    jpbdtA    = 2500,  & !: Max length of bdy field in file
    jpbdiM    = 2500,  & !: Max length of bdy field on a processor
    jpbtiM    = 100,   & !: Max number of time dumps per file
    jpbgrd    = 3,     !: Number of horizontal grid types used
                    ! (T, u, v, f)

  #else
  !!-----
  !!  Default option :                               NO open boundary condition
  !!-----
  LOGICAL, PUBLIC, PARAMETER ::  lk_bdy = .FALSE. !: Unstructured Ocean
                                              !Boundary Condition flag
  #endif

  !!=====
END MODULE bdy_par
    
```

Figure 14: FRS parameters in the *bdy_par* module.

3.2.3.2. Namelist variables

The namelist variables are shown on Figure 15.

```

!-----
!      nambdy      unstructured open boundaries parameters (#ifdef key_bdy)
!-----
!  filbdy_data_T = Name of data file at T-points
!  filbdy_data_U = Name of data file at U-points
!  filbdy_data_V = Name of data file at V-points
!  ln_bdy_clim   = .true.: It is assumed that bdy data files contain 1 or
!                  12 time dumps and that it is cyclic.
!  ln_bdy_vol    = .true.: Volume correction (see volbdy parameter)
!  nbdy_dta      = 0 the bdy data are equal to the initial state
!                  1 the bdy data are read in 'filbdy_data_X' NetCdf files
!  nb_rinwidth   = width of the relaxation zone
!  volbdy        = 0 the total water flux across open boundaries is zero
!                  1 the total volume of the system is conserved
&nambdy
  filbdy_data_T='bdydata_grid_T.nc'
  filbdy_data_U='bdydata_grid_U.nc'
  filbdy_data_V='bdydata_grid_V.nc'
  ln_bdy_clim=.false.
  ln_bdy_vol=.false.
  nbdy_dta = 0
  nb_rinwidth =7
  volbdy = 1
/
!-----
    
```

Figure 15: Namelist for the FRS scheme.

3.3. Testing

3.3.1. Model configuration

To validate the FRS, tests have been performed with a simple channel, quasi-identical to the experiment of Verron and Le Provost (1985). This configuration was originally designed to study the evolution of disturbances when a zonal jet is initialised over a seamount. As for Talandier and Tréguier (2002), It will be used here to study how well an open boundary scheme evacuates anomalies.

Parameter	value
Dimensions Lx x Ly x H	1000 km x 500 km x 4000 m
Number of points jpi x jpj x jpk	202 x 104 x 30
Horizontal resolution δx	5 km
Vertical resolution	≈ 120 m to 85 m
Seamount height hm and radius rm	800 m / 50 km
Time step	540 s
Biharmonic viscosity/diffusivity	$-5 \times 10^9 \text{ m}^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Vertical diffusivity/viscosity	$1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$

Table 2: Model parameters

The zonal channel, considered in the following, is an f-plan of length $L_x=1000$ km, width $L_y=500$ km and depth $H=4000$ m with two open boundaries at the Eastern and western ends (see Figure 16). The basin is initially filled with homogenous water and a constant barotropic Eastward jet of $0,1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ in equilibrium with the surface pressure gradient. The flow is perturbed by a gaussian topography anomaly of height $h_m=800$ m and radius $r_m=50$ km close to the western boundary. Vertical diffusion is constant and a biharmonic operator is used for the lateral subgrid mixing of momentum and tracers. The different parameters are summarised in Table 2.

Figure 16: Model configuration.

All the tests presented in the following have been performed in the multi-processors case on 4 Linux workstations.

3.3.2. Results

3.3.2.1. Straight open boundaries case

We consider here the basic case of two straight open boundaries, which allows comparisons with the existing OBC scheme in OPA. An additional simulation (REF) in an extended channel ($L_x=1500$ km) and specified boundaries will be used as a reference.

As a start, we obviously verified that the FRS gives the same results at machine accuracy as the OBC scheme with specified open boundaries. We then compared the FRS with the more complex radiative scheme of Raymond and Kuo (1984) combined to a weak relaxation term (RADIATIVE).

Maps on Figure 17 and Figure 18 show the time evolution of the relative vorticity during the 2 months of each experiment. As the simulation starts, a pair of eddies is formed over the topography anomaly. With the chosen parameters, the anticyclonic eddy remains trapped over the seamount while the cyclonic one is advected to the East by the mean flow until it reaches the open boundary around day 31. All schemes generate some noise at the eastern boundary and a strip of negative vorticity as the cyclone approaches. All in

all, the simple FRS with a relaxation zone width of one appears to work as well or even better than the radiative scheme (it was also noted by Talandier and Tréguier (2002)). However, increasing the relaxation zone to 7 points, overspecifies the eastern boundary and does not improve the results.

Figure 17: Relative vorticity after 7 (left) and 15 days (right) with different open boundary schemes.

Figure 18: Relative vorticity after 31 (left) and 60 days (right) with different open boundary schemes and straight open boundaries.

3.3.2.2. Unstructured open boundaries case

The unstructured case has finally been tested with an oblique open west boundary as shown on Figure 19. The configuration has first been run with a flat bottom to verify that no instabilities arise from the open boundary alone. As seen on Figure 19, the cyclonic eddy is dissipated with similar errors as in the straight boundary case.

Figure 19: Relative vorticity after 7 (left) and 26 days (right) with the FRS and unstructured open boundaries.

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